

Angelo Leogrando^{1*}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Fatal accidents at work in Europe

Between 2010 and 2020 they decreased by 23.71%

The indicator measures the number of fatal accidents that occur during the course of work and which lead to the death of the victim within one year of the accident. The incidence rate refers to the number of fatal accidents per 100,000 employed persons. An occupational injury is "a discrete event in the course of work which results in physical or mental harm". All accidents at work are included, whether they occurred inside or outside the employer's premises, accidents in public places or various means of transport during a trip during work (commuting accidents are excluded) and at home (such as during teleworking). It also includes cases of acute poisoning and malicious acts of other people, if these occurred during the course of work.

Ranking of European countries by value of fatal accidents at work per 100,000 workers in 2020. Cyprus ranks first in value of fatal accidents at work per 100,000 workers in 2020 with a value of 4.45 units, followed by Bulgaria with a value of 3.68, and from Italy with a value of 3.39 units. In the middle of the table are Slovenia with a value of 1.85, followed by Ireland with an amount of 1.79 and Estonia with a value of 1.73 units. Germany closes the ranking with a value of 0.73 units, followed by Sweden with a value of 0.49 units and the Netherlands with an amount of 0.3 units.

Ranking of European countries by the value of the percentage change in the value of fatal accidents at work per 100,000 workers between 2010 and 2020. Malta is in first place by the value of the percentage change in the value of fatal accidents with a value equal to 67.76% equal to an amount of 1.24 units, followed by Greece with a value of 20.55% equal to an amount of 0.15 units, and by Croatia with an amount of 17.96% equal to an amount of 0.44 unit. In the middle of the table are Ireland with an amount of -21.15% equal to an amount of -0.48 units, followed by Slovakia with an amount of 26.96% equal to an amount of -0.55 units and from Romania with a value of -1.6 units. The ranking is closed by Sweden with a value equal to -60.16%, followed by Poland with a value equal to -63.01% equal to an amount of -2.3 units and by the Netherlands with an amount of -65, 91% equal to an amount of -0.58 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. The data highlight the presence of two clusters, namely:

- Cluster 1: Lithuania, Latvia, Bulgaria, Portugal, Romania, Luxembourg, Austria, Estonia, France, Croatia;
- Cluster 2: Finland, Denmark, Norway, Germany, Switzerland, Sweden, Greece, Netherlands, Belgium, Spain, Slovakia, Hungary, Poland, Ireland, Slovenia, Cyprus, Italy, Czech Republic, Malta.

The value of the median of the clusters highlights the dominance of Cluster 1-C1 over Cluster 2-C2 with the following ordering of the clusters, namely: $C1=2.63 > C2=1.45$. From a geographical point

¹Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrando.cultore@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

of view, it appears that the value of accidents at work tends to be higher in the Baltic and Balkan countries, in France and in Portugal.

Network analysis with Euclidean distance. A network analysis is then applied using the Euclidean distance. Two complex network structures are identified. Particularly:

- Sweden and Germany have a connection amounting to 0.38 units;
- Germany has a connection with Sweden in the amount of 0.38 units and with Finland in the amount of 0.59 units;
- Finland has a connection with Germany in the amount of 0.59 units and with Denmark in the amount of 0.61 units;
- Denmark has a connection with Finland amounting to 0.61 units.

There is a complex network structure as follows:

- Ireland has a connection with Spain amounting to 0.56 units;
- Spain has a connection with Ireland with an amount of 0.56 units and with Hungary with an amount of 0.58 units.
- Hungary has a connection with Spain amounting to 0.58 units.

Conclusions. Between 2010 and 2020 the value of accidents at work decreased from an amount of 2.64 to a value of 2.01 units or a reduction equal to an amount of -23.71%. Of course, accidents in the workplace depend above all on the percentage of workers who work in sectors that can be considered dangerous, such as agriculture and construction. Indeed, countries that have a significant proportion of workers employed in the service sector also have a lower incidence of occupational accidents. Furthermore, there are other factors that can have an impact on the growth of the value of accidents at work such as, for example, the lack of adequate accident prevention legislation, the lack of a corporate culture of occupational safety, the poor professional qualification of workers on occupational safety issues. Furthermore, it is very probable that the value of accidents at work in Italy and Greece is much higher than that declared due to the presence of undeclared work especially in agriculture and construction. It therefore follows that the essential determinant for the reduction of accidents in the workplace is connected to the culture of safety and the adoption of anti-accident measures in companies. Finally, it is highly probable that at least a part of work accidents, especially in Italy, are not true and constitute real scams carried out to the detriment of social insurance. Therefore, more stringent controls are needed to prevent, on the one hand, undeclared workers from being overexposed to the risk of accidents and, on the other hand, regular workers from cheating on social insurance to pocket subsidies. Net of these two phenomena, there is a general need for a growth in social protection devices against accidents at work with targeted actions towards companies, with specific certification, and with the use of digital tools to verify the adoption of adequate safety procedures in the execution of the works.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

References

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. *Available at SSRN*.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). Fixed Broadband Take-Up in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4034298*.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. *Available at SSRN 4355016*.

Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4091597*.

Laureti, L., Massaro, A., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Renewable Electricity Output on Sustainability in the Context of Circular Economy: A Global Perspective. *Sustainability*, 15(3), 2160.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. *Available at SSRN*.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3983218*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. *Available at SSRN 4414232*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. *Available at SSRN 4398483*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Regulatory Quality and ESG Model at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4388957*.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4466452*.

Appendix

